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Design and Simulation of Reliable Desuperheating Methods for a Multi-Stage Oil-Free R718 Compressor for High-Temperature Heat Pumps

Introduction

High-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) are key to support industrial decarbonization, and innovation is under progress to meet demands above 150 °C. Water (R718) is a promising refrigerant for such temperatures. However, excessive discharge temperatures and large compression ratios remain challenges, limiting practical applications. Desuperheating between compression stages is essential to limit operating temperatures in R718 compressors.

This work presents the design and simulation of a desuperheating system tailored for an innovative oil-free, multi-stage reciprocating compressor using R718. Designed for integration into HTHPs delivering up to 185°C, the compressor operates at sub-atmospheric suction and relies on coated compression chambers, highly sensitive to liquid droplets. This feature poses specific challenges for safe and effective steam desuperheating

Methods

The compressor used in the HTHP has a discharge temperature limit of 260 °C. Due to the risk of liquid droplets entering the oil-free compression chambers, direct injection was ruled out. Instead, two two-step desuperheating concepts were explored. The first uses dedicated heat exchangers for each stage to evaporate high-pressure water and mix it with the vapor stream. The second begins desuperheating in a gravity-driven evaporator and finalizes it with controlled and reduced liquid injection. Both approaches, represented below, aim to achieve 20 K superheat at each stage.

The superheating of the 1st compression stage remains to be adjusted, since the vapor drawn from the LP DRAIN is at saturated conditions and a 20 K superheat is also required here. In the first concept, heat is provided by superheated steam discharged from the 4th compression stage. In the second concept, an electric heater is used, and its power consumption is included in the HTHP COP calculation.

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Results and discussion

The system shows significantly improved performance when the second desuperheating concept is applied, with the combined effect of the desuperheating in the gravity-driven heat exchanger and 1st stage superheating with electric heater. Under equivalent conditions, the HTHP's heating capacity is 19–26% higher with the second desuperheating concept, while the COP increases by 7–19%.

Due to the relatively low suction temperature at the compressor second stage (DESUP1), injection is always necessary, and the fraction handled by the gravity-driven evaporator is lower than in other stages (DESUP2 and DESUP3). For the fourth compression stage (DESUP3), the gravity-driven heat exchanger can handle all desuperheating up to 160 °C. The contribution of the gravity-driven heat exchanger decreases as the thermal oil inlet temperature rises.

As the thermal oil inlet temperature increases, the discharge temperature approaches, and in some cases exceeds, the limit specified by the compressor manufacturer (indicated by the black dashed line). This outcome is expected, given the large temperature lift achieved with only four compression stages.

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